

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE ARAMID FELT HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

Non-woven felts made of high-strength fibres have superb performance to stop projectiles due to extensive deformation capabilities. In this work, a non-woven needle-punched aramid felt "Twaron[®] Felt No.9" impacting by 6.35 mm steel ball was studied numerically and experimentally for better understanding of the main energy dissipation mechanisms. C++ based truss finite element model of felt with stochastic fibre's distribution was developed and implemented with LS-Dyna package. Some microstructure investigations as well as individual fibre's tensile tests were performed to obtain initial data for model. Moreover, ballistic tests of one, three and five layers of felt were carried out. Experimental ballistic limits V_{50} are compared with the numerical ones and a good agreement is noticed including frictional pull-out and fibre's fracture mechanisms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Non-woven felts are materials that are composed of a set randomly oriented polymer or natural fibres bonded by either thermal, mechanical or chemical bonds. Felt's stiffness and strength are not as well as in woven fabrics, but they exhibit remarkable ductility and energy absorption capabilities. Non-woven felts based on high-strength and high-performance fibres are used for many applications such as insulations, fire barriers, geotextiles, filters, stab protection etc. [1].

Mechanical behaviour of non-woven fabrics is highly complicated because involve different micromechanical processes that take place simultaneously: fibre straightening, sliding and failure, bond breakage and continuous rearrangement of the initial fibre network configuration [2, 3].

Many researchers have carried out detailed analysis of the micromechanisms of non-woven felts deformation and fracture. Several techniques were used to simulate a mechanical behaviour of non-woven materials. For example, Jearanaisilawong [2] studied failure mechanisms of needle-punched polyethylene non-woven felt Dyneema[®] Fraglight NW201 under quasi-static loading conditions. Based on these data three-dimensional, large strain continuum model for the constitutive behaviour of non-woven felts was proposed and implemented as a VUMAT subroutine in ABAQUS finite element code. Ridruejo et al. [3-7] presented similar investigation for glass-fibre non-woven felt and geotextile made of thermally consolidated polypropylene fibres. Demirci et al. [8, 9] developed a continuum model to explain the stress-strain behaviour of thermally bonded non-woven fabric made of PA/PE bicomponent fibres. Random orientation of individual fibres is quantified in terms of the orientation distribution function in order to determine the material's anisotropy. Silberstein et al. [9] proposed an approach based on RVE-based technique to predict a macroscopic behaviour of the non-woven electrospun mat. The model consists of a triangulated framework and uses a homogenisation technique to predict a

response of the mat under monotonic and cyclic loading. Nowadays microstructure-based models with explicit account of individual fibres by using truss elements become popular for analysing non-woven fabric deformations and fracture behaviour [10-20]. These modelling approaches are computationally not as efficient as a continuum one; however, it may describe all the main deformation and fracture mechanisms of felts.

Nevertheless, all above models can be used only for quasi-static problems. Non-woven felts made of high-strength fibres have excellent capabilities to stop fragments of exploding munitions [21]. A continuum modelling approach allows predicting just the wave propagation patterns in non-woven ballistic material [22]. In connection with this, it is necessary to develop a numerical model that allows predicting accurately the behaviour of non-woven material subjected to high-velocity impact.

In this work, non-woven aramid fabric Twaron[®] felt was considered for ballistic protection. A finite-element model based on nonwoven's microstructure and properties of constituent fibres was developed and implemented with LS-Dyna. Finite element mesh was generated by using the self-created program. The trusses in the model were straight and randomly filled the sample volume. Specific through-thickness connections were used to take into account mechanical bonding (needle-punching) of fibrous mat. Numerical simulations of one, three and five layers of felt subjected to 6.35 mm steel ball impact were carried out. The supercomputer «RSC Tornado SUSU» (190th position in world TOP500) was used for calculations because of a great numerical size of model.

Obtained ballistic limits V_{50} and full ballistic curves are compared with the experimental data of ballistic tests and a good agreement is obtained including the mechanisms of deformation.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Material

In this work, a web of high strength and mechanically interlocking (needle-punching) staple fibres manufactured by Teijin Aramid “Twaron[®] Felt No.9” [23] is used for ballistic investigations. Nominal felt areal density is 350 g/m². Upon inspection, it is found that the fabric is composed of 50 mm long filaments. The fibre's diameter was measured from microphotographs taken in optical microscope Olympus BX51. The average fibre diameter was 11 μm.

Investigated material had specific through-thickness connections by needle-punching. Fig. 1 shows that the punch pattern in Twaron[®] Felt No.9 is close to random.

Figure 1: Random bonding pattern in Twaron[®] Felt No.9.

To study the felt structure after needle-punching a specimen of the felt was filled by polyester resin, cured, cut into thin plates and observed in optical microscopy. Specimen cross-section is shown in Fig. 2.

This image shows that during needle-punching web of fibres stitched through the thickness by fibre's bundles in curved form.

Figure 2: Through-thickness connections in microstructure of Twaron® Felt No.9 after needle-punching.

2.2 Single fibre static tests

Single fibre tensile tests were carried out with a mechanical testing machine Instron 5942 equipped with a 10 N load cell to obtain the quasi-static mechanical properties of the fibres. Individual fibres were extracted from the fabric by carefully pulling with tweezers. After this, fibres were gripped in rubber serrated pneumatic side action grips Instron 2712-019. These grips have a high coefficient of friction, providing a reliable value of tensile strength measurement. The nominal stress was computed from the applied load and the average fibre cross sectional area. The fibre's elastic modulus value was $E = 90$ GPa based on the data of [23-25].

It was obtained that a mean value of an ultimate fibre tensile stress is $\sigma_u = 2.53 \pm 0.52$ GPa. A significant scatter in the failure strength most likely related to the initial fibre's kinking, damage after mechanical bonding, extracting, and difference of fibre's diameters.

2.3 Ballistic tests

Specimens with dimensions of $100 \text{ mm} \times 100 \text{ mm}$ and composed of one, three and five layers of Twaron® Felt No.9 were prepared for ballistic tests. Felt layers were simply stacked together without additional connecting. Ballistic tests were conducted according to standard GOST 50744-95 [26] using 6.35 mm steel ball weighing 1.05 g.

Special powder gun stand capable of accelerating the projectiles up to 900 m/s was used (Fig. 3). Specimens were placed freely between two Lexan plates ($110 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm} \times 4 \text{ mm}$ with open hole of 67 mm diameter) with strictly fixed distance between them for each specimen type. After this, plates with specimen were vice gripped. A compact optical chronograph with 75 mm of base for start/stop time measurement determined initial projectile's velocity.

Figure 3: The gun assembly used for ballistic tests.

Special frictional trap weighing 665 g (coefficient of dry sliding friction along the rail was 0.27) was used to projectile's residual momentum measurement. Residual velocity is calculated by the formula

$$V(S) = \left(1 + \frac{m}{M}\right) \sqrt{2g \cdot f \cdot S}, \quad (1)$$

where S is trap sliding distance, m is the mass of projectile, M is the mass of trap, f is coefficient of sliding friction and g is acceleration of gravity.

Fig. 4 shows the residual velocity vs. initial velocity curves obtained with 32 shots. The symbols are actual tests measurements. After determining the speeds of the ball before and after impact, experimental data were fitted by least-square regression according to the classical Lambert-Jonas equation [27]:

$$V_r = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } V_i < V_{50} \\ A \cdot (V_i^k - V_{50}^k)^{1/k} & \text{if } V_i \geq V_{50} \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where A , V_{50} and k are regression parameters. V_r and V_i are the residual and initial velocities of the projectile, respectively, V_{50} is the ballistic limit velocity.

The ballistic limits, values of A and k given by fitting are shown in Table 1.

Number of layers	Ballistic limit V_{50} , m/s	A	k
1	280	0.983	3.534
3	420	1.005	3.511
5	486	1.029	3.324

Table 1: Lambert-Jonas equation parameters for various number of Twaron® Felt No.9 layers.

Figure 4: Lambert-Jonas fits with actual tests measurements for residual velocity vs. initial velocity of the 6.35 steel ball for 1, 3 and 5 layers of Twaron® Felt No.9.

When initial velocity did not exceed ballistic limit back-face signature (permanent deflection of back face) increases gradually with projectile's velocity increasing. The maximum deflections as well as significant fibre's pull-out are obtained at velocities close to V_{50} (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: One layer specimen of Twaron[®] Felt No.9 and projectile after impact at a velocity of 293 m/s.

With further increasing of projectile's velocity back-face signature decrease and the dominant failure mode is the fibre's failure (Fig. 6). No serious fibres pull-outs were observed at high velocity of steel ball.

Figure 6: One layer specimen of Twaron[®] Felt No.9 after impact at a velocity of 804 m/s.

3 FELT MODELLING

3.1 Program for creating 3D model of felt

A specimen of the felt (Twaron[®] Felt No.9) with size $100 \times 100 \times 3.5$ mm contains more than 450 000 fibres (diameter of 11 microns) which randomly distributed over the sample volume. Manually creating the model of felt is an extremely difficult task. Therefore, the program for creating 3D model of felt was developed by using C++ language. The received models of felt were used to calculate in the software LS-Dyna.

The program offers a graphic user interface for creating a felt with straight fibres. At the user interface, it is possible to enter the following values: dimensions of sample volume along the axes X, Y and Z; fibre length; the size of the finite elements; number of fibres (to have possibility of variation of areal density of felt). The program creates a file with the extension .k (input file for calculation in the software LS-Dyna) with the coordinates of nodes and 'truss' finite elements of felt with straight fibres.

The fibres are uniformly distributed throughout the sample volume.

The algorithm of the program includes the following steps:

1. Input parameters by user.
2. Creating a predetermined amount of fibres:
 - 2.1 random generation of coordinates starting node for each fibre within the sample volume;
 - 2.2 random generation of deflection angles for each fibre relatively to the axes X, Y and Z;
 - 2.3 calculating the coordinates of following nodes and verify attachments of these nodes to sample volume.
3. Writing the coordinates of nodes and finite elements to a file with the extension *.k*.

3.2 Description of 3D model of felt

Fibres of non-woven felt were modelled by truss finite elements (*SECTION_BEAM, EQ.3). Trusses in the model were straight with a length of 50 mm. Through-thickness connections (Fig. 2) were taken into account in the model as follows: there were created finite elements located on the edges of the parallelepipeds, which are not connected to each other. The edges of parallelepipeds had dimensions of 2×2 mm in the plane and 3.5 mm through single-layer specimen thickness (Fig. 7). The dimensions of additional truss network and the trusses diameter were selected based on the number of holes after needle-punching as well as an average numbers of fibres into transversal 'thread'. The cross section of the truss was increased 7 times in comparison with the real fibre to reduce the problem of computational cost. The material of truss was linear elastic up to failure. Tensile strength of truss was 2.53 GPa (experiment) with interfibre's friction coefficient 0.4 [28]. Elastic modulus was 90 GPa, Poisson's ratio was 0.2, density was 1440 kg/m^3 [23-25]. Felt specimen was not clamped. Numerical simulations were carried out for specimens with one, three and five felt layers with explicit integration scheme. Finite element mesh for one layer is shown in Fig. 8. Projectile velocity varied from 300 to 600 m/s. Projectile material was steel with liner elasticity.

3D models of non-woven felt had a great numerical size. So, the calculations of high-velocity impact on non-woven felt were provided with the LS-DYNA software with use of the supercomputer.

Figure 7: Additional truss network.

4 COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DATA

A comparison of pictures of deformation and failure of one layer of felt is shown in Fig. 9. Lambert-Jonas fits of experimental data with numerical data for residual velocity vs. initial velocity of the projectile for 1, 3 and 5 layers of 3D model of felt are shown in Fig. 10. With an initial velocity of the projectile, more than 500 m/s numerical residual velocities are below the Lambert-Jonas fits of experimental data. This is because this model does not include heat generation effects.

1) Top view

2) Front view

Figure 8: Finite element mesh (1 layer of felt).

In addition, the model of one layer of felt with diameter increased 4 times in comparison with the real fibre was created. Calculations of high-velocity impact on this non-woven felt were performed. A comparison of the residual velocities is carried out for the models with increased cross sections of the truss with the real 7 and 4 times. The difference did not exceed of 1%. Nevertheless, calculation of one shot for 5 layer's target took 24 hours with use of 48 cores (Intel Xeon X5680 processor).

Figure 9: Pictures of deformation and fracture of felt material (1 layer, the initial projectile velocity is 497 m/s).

Figure 10: Lambert-Jonas fits of experimental data (lines) with numerical data for residual velocity vs. initial velocity of the projectile for 1, 3 and 5 layers of 3D model of felt.

5 CONCLUSION

An assessment of the Twaron[®] Felt No.9 high velocity impact resistance was studied by means of 3D model of felt and experimental tests.

Analysis of microstructures of felt was held for assign parameters in the 3D model of felt with use of optical microscopy. Experiments to determine the tensile strength of the fibres were carried out.

Ballistic tests were conducted using 6.35 mm steel ball weighing 1.05 g and specimens with dimensions of 100 mm × 100 mm and composed of one, three and five layers of Twaron[®] Felt No.9. Experimental data were fitted by least-square regression according to the classical Lambert-Jonas equation.

The program for creating 3D model of felt was developed by using C ++ language. The calculations of high-velocity impact on non-woven felt (1, 3, 5 layers) were provided with the LS-Dyna software with supercomputer for lower dimensional 3D model of felt. The good agreement of experimental and numerical data was observed.

So we can further use of created 3D felt model to assess the ballistic performance of arbitrary numbers of felt layers and its combination with fabrics and steel/ceramic plates.

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